

THE ORIGIN OF LIFE, AND THE DESTRUCTION OF WORLDS

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Abstract

Levels of life arise from controlled mass destruction. We propose categorizing life as a fractal composed of 6-levels of increasing complexity and size, where each individual at a given level is an ecosystem of species from previous levels. We theorize that the transition between levels starts with the acquisition of a power of mass destruction, i.e. an ability to promptly target and destroy other species with little resistance. This ability leads to the vast and quick expansion of the transitioning species that starts to dominate, control, and modify the surrounding ecosystem. However, the transitioning species faces risks of self-annihilation due to self-harm and over-consumption of resources. To survive, it is constrained into creating a collaborative ecosystem where processes are more efficient at gathering resources, building infrastructure, and processing/transferring information/resources, thus yielding a higher-level species. From this perspective, **our theory provides a single explanation for the origin of life, the origin of complex life, the Cambrian explosion, the origin of human civilization, and beyond.** We further generalize the notions of information processing, domestication, automation, and consciousness to all species, and we explain their role in the transition between levels.

Cataclysmic events are known to be massive triggers of evolutionary changes. This work answers the question: *what happens when a species controls cataclysmic events to its advantage? The answer is life.*

Figure 1. Visual abstract of the levels of life, their destructive power, and information power. Notice how the PMDs of even-numbered levels are similar to the previous level but at a larger scale.

Disclaimer

The current work proposes a theory that intersects many different fields, such as physics, informatics, biochemistry, biology, psychology, neuroscience, and human history. The authors do not claim to be experts in all these fields; therefore, readers should expect minor inaccuracies, despite the considerable effort made by the authors in ensuring that most of the theory and the elements proposed hold. By presenting a general theory of life, the authors ask the readers to focus on the big picture and hope that publishing the theory will allow other scientists to fill up the missing details and improve the accuracy related to their field.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Premise

There are many mysteries regarding the origin of life and complex life. How and why did life originate? Will the same event happen again? Did it happen multiple times? One of the most prominent theories, namely the Primordial soup [1], [2] proposed by Darwin, states that the world was a soup of chemical building blocks, including essential proteins, amino acids, and RNA, and that this soup allowed the spontaneous formation of prokaryotes and viruses. The RNA-world is another theory claiming that viruses were the first form of life and that prokaryotes emerged from them [3]. However, it does not explain the process behind the origin of viruses nor the transformation into prokaryotes. Recent theories focus on the origin of life inside hydrothermal vents since they present many interesting characteristics, but they still do not provide an explicit mechanism [2]. Others look at auto-catalytic networks for the origin of self-reproducing complex organic molecules [4], [5]. On a completely different premise, the panspermia theory [6] states that the origin of life happened outside of Earth but does not answer how life formed.

Further, the mechanism in which bacterial life gave rise to complex life is also a mystery. A well-known aspect is that the phagocytosis of early archaea by bacteria became a symbiosis that forms the eukaryotic cell and its mitochondria [2], [7], [8]. However, the reason for this symbiosis and the mechanism that led to complex life is still subject to research.

These events are challenging to explain from the standard Darwinism theory since natural selection is about slow changes and guarantees to find transitioning species. Instead, the origin of life seems to fit better the theories that extreme events are significant evolutionary drivers [9], [10] since there appear to be no transition species and the major events seem to have happened quickly.

Again, from a Darwinism perspective, abilities that give a substantial advantage are often developed independently in different species. This effect is known as convergent evolution and can be observed notably in the evolution of wings [11], [12], or crab-shaped animals. However, prokaryotes, complex life, and complex animals each have a single ancestor. Hence, despite the substantial advantage to the new species, convergent evolution never happened. Again, this leaves a gap in standard evolutionary theory that brings the following question: *Why does life or complex life not have multiple origins?*

1.2 Nomenclature

To simplify the terminology used through the paper, L_n is used to denote “a species at level n ”. Multiple variants of this notation are present in Table 1.

Table 1. Nomenclature depicting the different terminology to denote the levels of life.

Notation	Definition	Example
L_n	A species at any given level n .	L_3 is the 3 rd level of life, namely the Eukaryotes.
$L_{n,m}$	A species at level n or m .	$L_{3,4}$ are the 3 rd or 4 th level of life.
$L_{<n}$	Any species at a level lower than n .	$L_{<3}$ are the species $L_{0,1,2}$, namely building blocks, viruses, and prokaryotes.
$L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$	A life transitioning from level L_n to level L_{n+1} .	$L_{2 \rightarrow 3}$ represents the species transitioning from the prokaryote to the eukaryote level.

1.3 Overview of the proposed theory

The theory's primary contribution is the realization that the different levels (complexities) of life can be explained from a common theory, considering small changes in the standard classification of species. It explains that a transition to a higher level starts when a species acquires a power of mass destruction (PMD), meaning that it controls an ability to destroy and consume other species with very little resistance. This change brings a significant perturbation that destroys the ecosystem's equilibrium and forces the transitioning species to reorganize into larger and more complex groups. The proposed PMDs are: *targeted catalysis* → *targeted gene editing* → *phagocytosis* → *complete digestive tract* → *fire* → *nuclear bomb*.

This work is compatible with standard biological theories, including the primordial soup [1], [2], the RNA-world [3], and the endosymbiosis [7], [8], as it generalizes the three events into a single theory. Additionally, it shows how the theory extends to other species and explains the Cambrian explosion [13], the emergence of viruses, and human civilization (Planeta Hominis).

Life is viewed as a fractal, meaning that each species is an ecosystem of smaller species, which is itself an ecosystem of smaller species until the basic building blocks are reached. A formal definition of life is presented at the end of the paper in section "4.11 A new definition of life". The fractal of life is illustrated in Figure 2. It comprises 6 levels, with each level characterized by the PMD it controls. An additional level-0 is used to categorize the basic building blocks of life (organic molecules, amino acids, lipid membranes).

PMD Power of mass destruction

We define a PMD as an ability developed by a given species to selectively and promptly destroy and consume any competing life-form that does not possess this power.

An example is how fire allowed the homo species to dominate the planet.

Figure 2. Illustration of the fractal nature of life. The even levels are represented as circles to illustrate that they are closed ecosystems. The odd levels are represented as connected rectangles to illustrate that elements are connected, but somewhat independent in that they can be cut in half while remaining a valid life form.

Fractals

Fractals are structures that exhibit self-similarities or repetitions at different scales. They are usually used in geometry to describe high-complexity shapes (e.g., trees, lungs, Romanesco broccoli). Here, we use them to describe the similar organizational structures observed at different levels of life.

A clear distinction is made between the odd-numbered levels and even-numbered levels since they exhibit some different characteristics. Odd levels (1,3,5) are small communities that behave somewhat similarly to their previous level. However, even levels (2,4,6) constitute giant communities of closed ecosystems and completely change their way of life.

The levels of life can also be distinguished by other characteristics that co-evolved with the PMD. First, before mastering the PMD, a living must achieve a basic form of a new level of information processing to ensure efficient control of the power. The observed information powers are RNA → DNA → Epigenome → Neurons → Speech → Computing. The information power starts at a basic level but increases quickly with the transition and the PMD control. Further, consciousness increases by co-evolving with the PMD since it helps the transitioning species maximize productivity while avoiding self-harm and over-consumption.

Figure 3 presents the 6 levels and their destructive abilities, with more details in the following sub-sections. Level L_0 is used to represent the primordial soup made of chemical building blocks. Human civilization is currently at the level $L_{5 \rightarrow 6}$, a transition state between levels 5 and 6.

Figure 3. A visual summary of the different levels of life and their characteristics. A more detailed summary is given later in Table 2. Even levels have the same color as the previous level but with a darker taint, highlighting that they have a similar but larger PMD and are composed of the same individuals but with a more complex structure.

1.4 Claims of the proposed theory

The current theory encompasses various subjects, including the classification of life, the origin of life, the origin and future of human civilization, information theory, consciousness theory, and more. To better grasp the different elements covered, the primary claims are summarized below.

Present a multi-leveled theory of life where the standard classification of species is replaced by a fractal representation of different levels, with a species at level n (L_n) characterized mainly by its power of mass destruction (PMD).

Generalize the origin of life, complex life, Cambrian explosion, civilization, and more into a single theory, with each transition occurring via similar steps. First, the species starts the transition by acquiring a primitive control over a PMD; then, it increases its complexity to improve its control over the PMD, expand faster and avoid self-destruction.

Present a multi-leveled theory of information processing that explains how the ability to store, execute, process, and transfer information increases in speed and complexity with each level. This fundamental step is necessary to control the PMD without self-harm.

Generalize consciousness to all levels of life. Lower levels of consciousness include an understanding of when to reproduce and the detection of threats. Higher levels of consciousness allow understanding and optimizing self-behavior and sub-components.

Explain the lack of intermediate species since the only way a species can survive a transition is to expand and complete the transition rapidly before running out of resources or space and before being outcompeted relative to the PMD. Hence, there are no intermediate species between virus/prokaryotes nor prokaryotes/eukaryotes. The first species to complete the transitions will control all resources and territory.

Propose experiments to reproduce the origin of life by doing in-vitro or in-silico simulations that favor the apparition of a PMD. However, the proposed experiments are extremely expensive to execute with current technology.

2 Transition between levels, and how to avoid self-destruction

The current theory is based on the idea that a new level of life L_{n+1} appears after the acquisition of a power of mass destruction (PMD) from a life L_n , thus completely unbalancing the ecosystem. This is complementary to the Darwinism theory of slow and random changes [14] that assumes such a drastic change would likely cause the extinction of the transitioning species by self-annihilation or resource extinction. For example, a species of fox that evolves to become twice as fast as rabbits will exhaust its resources.

If the proposed theory of controlled PMD is true, how do these transitioning species avoid self-annihilation from the PMD? How did all the RNA strands not catalyze each other into destruction? How did eukaryotic cells avoid contamination of their DNA during phagocytosis, or avoid ingesting their own colonies? How did humans not extinguish themselves by burning all surrounding them? Or how did they gather enough resources to sustain the population growth?

This section allows answering the mentioned concerns. It discusses how larger and more complex societies, better information processing, transformation, domestication, automation, and consciousness are fundamental for a species to survive its own PMD. Without these, a transitioning species will quickly become extinct without reaching the next level. Multiple characteristics must co-evolve with the PMD for the transitioning life to be sustainable.

Below is a summary of the points discussed in this section.

2.1 Beyond Darwinism. Darwinism cannot explain large and fast changes, meaning it fails to explain the origin of life or the transition between levels.

2.2 Power of mass destruction (PMD). Controlling a PMD is the most important step for transitioning to a new level since it allows a given species to modify the environment to its needs.

Key ideas

Transitioning to a higher level has many risks; a bad control of the PMD can cause self-harm, and population expansion can cause starvation.

2.3 Size expansion. A significant increase in population sizes is necessary to improve control over the PMD and to avoid self-annihilation.

2.4 New information power. Mastering a PMD requires co-evolving a new information processing power, i.e., an ability to process and transfer higher-level information faster.

2.5 Transformation. The transitioning species will transform most of its environment into useful resources to avoid exhausting them from the fast expansion.

2.6 Domestication. Odd level species will domesticate other species in their environment to increase resource throughput. Even level species will expand on this domestication.

2.7 Automated machines. Even level species will develop automated machines to process/transport resources or detect/destroy threats.

2.8 Consciousness. Consciousness is generalized beyond the human mind to all living things, with each level exhibiting its form of consciousness.

2.9 After the transition: Back to the equilibrium. The ecosystem's equilibrium is broken during the transition to a new level, but a new equilibrium is reached when the transition is completed.

2.1 Beyond Darwinism

Darwinism is the leading theory of evolution and claims that changes happen slowly over time via slow mutations [14]. Although it is widely accepted and works very well around an equilibrium, many have proposed that the most important evolutionary changes happen quickly following drastic environmental changes [9], [10]. For example, biodiversity significantly increases during or after mass extinction events since the entire ecosystem changes, and life must adapt and find a new equilibrium.

Along the same lines, the proposed theory states that a transition between levels $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$ happen during mass extinction events, with the main difference being that a species at level L_n triggers the mass extinction in a controlled way. Hence, as the life transitions from L_n to L_{n+1} , it rapidly creates major changes and mass extinctions, thus triggering the whole ecosystem to adapt around it. A few species can evolve to evade or survive the PMD, while most will become domesticated or symbionts.

After completion of the transition, the ecosystem reaches a new equilibrium, and the usage of the PMD is reduced. For example, most eukaryotes no longer use phagocytosis to feed; they use it for their immune system.

Key ideas

From a Darwinism point of view, changes need to be slow and steady to stay in equilibrium. The proposed theory states that some minor phenotypic changes can bring extraordinary advantages. For instance, the acquisition of a PMD by a given species allows it to destroy the equilibrium and modify surrounding ecosystems to its needs.

There is direct evidence of these major events at various times in the planet's history. First, the Cambrian explosion is known to have caused a rapid and vast increase in biodiversity [13] and is correlated with the apparition of the complete digestive tract [15]. Then, the mass extinction of large mammals happened as early human tribes populated the regions [16], correlated with an increase in diversity of human tribes (culture and spirituality evolve similarly to DNA). Finally, the 6th mass extinction of animals is happening as human civilizations grow [17].

Darwinism does not explain this fast change since breaking the equilibrium often leads to the extinction of the L_{n+1} specie. For example, in the predator/prey setting of fox versus rabbit, the fox is rarely successful in its hunt to avoid the extinction of the rabbit population. If a fox becomes as fast, it will be much more successful in the short term, but there will not be any rabbit left to feed on after a few generations, especially considering the high energy required for faster speed. However, if the fox becomes 2% faster, rabbits can adapt to these small changes, and natural selection will also favor rabbits that are 2% faster.

Darwinism states that most genetic mutations are small and bring minor phenotypic changes in the species [14]. However, this theory argues that some small phenotypic changes can bring an extraordinarily powerful advantage, namely the acquisition of the PMD. Most species cannot adapt fast enough against these changes, and many will go extinct. For example, the early acquisition of fire by the homo genus required minimal DNA changes compared to other homo or even apes. However, it provided an incomparable advantage, enabling the homo to develop more complex tribes and destroy entire ecosystems.

2.2 Power of mass destruction (PMD)

When a species L_n starts controlling a PMD, it means that it has evolved a power to quickly and selectively eradicate a large group of competing L_n species while exploiting the resource generated from this destruction. Selectivity is essential to avoid destroying all available resources at once, avoid exterminating beneficial species, and avoid self-harm. Further, the destruction must be fast and efficient, such that other species cannot quickly adapt to it.

The observed destructive powers on Earth are: targeted catalysis → targeted editing → phagocytosis → digestive tract → fire → nuclear energy. Notice how every even level $L_{2,4,6}$ has a very similar PMD to its previous odd level $L_{1,3,5}$ but on a larger scale. Targeted editing is a larger equivalent of targeted catalysis, the complete digestive tract is a larger equivalent of phagocytosis, and nuclear energy is a larger equivalent of fire.

Note that this theory states that the L_1 species originated first from RNA thanks to its ability to selectively destroy and transform other molecules with targeted catalysis. This premise is aligned perfectly with the recent theory that the RNA-first world originated thanks to catalysis [18], allowing early RNA strands to transform arbitrary

Extreme events

Extreme and cataclysmic events, such as natural disasters, reduce the diversity of ecosystems in the short term. But in the longer term, they trigger the apparition of new ecosystems, sometimes with greater diversity. A well-known example is the asteroid that ended the dinosaur era but started the era of birds and mammals.

Key ideas

The control of the PMD is the most important step for the evolution of a new level of life. It is about selectively annihilating competing species while exploiting their resources.

organic molecules into functional building blocks, including amino acids and nucleic acids.

Further, the Cambrian explosion and the rise of the Homo genus also coincided, respectively, with the development of a complete digestive tract [15], [19] and the control of fire [20].

2.3 Size expansion

It is easy to see why an increase in size and population size is necessary to avoid self-destruction from the PMD. For levels 1 and 2 (targeted catalysis and targeted editing), a longer genetic code allows redundancy of the genomic information and dedicated genetic information to sustain a protein shell or a cellular wall. For levels 3 and 4 (phagocytosis and digestive tract), a big enough group of cells becomes difficult to ingest completely. For levels 5 and 6 (fire and nuclear bombs), a larger human population allows building walls, defense systems, and redundancy of humans and cities.

Population sizes usually increase by a factor of $10^2 - 10^6$ at each level, but there is no clear rule regarding the increase. It can depend on multiple factors such as the nature of the PMD, the elapsed time between transitions, and the resources and land availability.

There is a noticeable difference between the population increase that happens at odd levels versus even levels. Odd levels $L_{1,3,5}$ are a colony/tribe of previous level species, but where each individual maintains relative independence. For even levels $L_{2,4,6}$, there is a greater social structure composed of living 2 levels below, with a hyper-specialization and a loss of independence of the components.

Hence, the individuals composing an *odd-level* species can survive alone, whether the individuals in an *even-level* life cannot survive by themselves except during reproduction. E.g., mRNA cannot reproduce outside the cell, individual cells cannot survive outside an animal body, and individual humans cannot survive on any planet outside of their own.

Note that a significant increase in size requires improved information processing, resource sharing, and consciousness, subject to future sections. Section 2.4 explains how the new information power is fundamental to controlling the PMD and coordinating all components of the transitioning species. Sections 2.6 and 2.7 explain how domestication and machines increase resource production and sharing to sustain the larger population. Section 2.8 explains how a higher consciousness enables the synchronization of the needs and avoids war within itself.

Key ideas

Bigger population sizes give a survival advantage against a PMD.

Population size

Population size of a life L_n is defined as the number of livings at the closest even level. E.g., the number of humans for $L_{5,6}$ or the number of cells for $L_{3,4}$.

2.4 New information power

The increase in group size necessarily requires improving information exchange and communications. To avoid other species adapting to the PMD, the destructive power must be much faster than the information processing speed of previous levels. For example, targeted catalysis allows useful chemical reactions to happen faster than arbitrary reactions, digestion happens faster than the epigenome can adapt a resistance, and fire burns faster than most animals can learn to avoid it.

Hence, the speed of information processing becomes fundamental for the transitioning species. The only way to avoid self-destruction and fully control a PMD is to process and update higher levels of information at a greater speed than the destructive power itself.

However, since information processing speed relies on chemical/physical processes, minor mutations cannot significantly increase the speed. Instead, a new type of information power must emerge before developing the PMD. As the control over the PMD improves and the population size increases, the information power will also improve in co-evolution.

The observed information powers on Earth are the following: RNA → DNA → epigenetics → neurons → language → computing.

The information power can be studied from a computer science perspective by looking at the equivalent functions available to programmers and machine learning scientists. These functions are `write/run/copy` → `function/find/edit` → `if/multiply/import` → `wait/while/fit` → `teach/count/trade` → `evaluate/predict/thread`, with more details given in Table 2 at the end of the section.

The emergence of the new information power is a fundamental co-evolution step that always happens when acquiring a PMD. It often precedes the destructive power by millions of years in different species but stays at a basic stage, but only the species that controls the PMD transitions to the next level. Once the PMD is acquired, the information power becomes an essential part of survival and improves via co-evolution with the PMD.

In addition, ensuring coordination and synchronization of all components of a larger species requires a higher information power. For example, a single government cannot rule planets from different solar systems since it will take many years for any decision to reach them. The same is true at smaller scales. For example, epigenome allows eukaryotic colonies to adapt faster than DNA, and neurons allow animals to adapt faster than epigenome.

This section contradicts many theories that place human intelligence and tool use as the primary step of building an advanced society [21]. Instead, it explains why other primates, elephants, dolphins, ravens, or octopuses did not create societies despite being intelligent, able to communicate and use tools [22]. Although basic forms of

Key ideas

To control a PMD, a transitioning species requires a new information power that allows processing information faster than the destruction.

Information power

Information power is a new, faster, and more powerful way to process and transmit information. It goes from storage and execution in RNA/DNA to sensing and learning in animals and computing in *Planeta Hominis*.

intelligence and communication are pre-requisite of the transition $L_{4 \rightarrow 5}$, it is the PMD (fire) that allowed the development of advanced human tribes [23], [24]. Human intelligence and communication skills became superior thanks to the co-evolution with fire, enabling humans to avoid self-destruction by improving their control over fire and their ability to live in large groups. Due to the high energy requirement, scientists have difficulty explaining how humans' brain-to-body ratio became so large [21]. However, it becomes a lesser problem considering that fire significantly increases access to resources.

2.5 Transformation

Destroying other species without consuming them is not a sustainable way of growing. Instead, during the transition, a species $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$ must use its PMD in a way to transform other species into energy or useful components.

This behavior is observed in L_5 human tribes, where not only do humans have a high-variety diet, but they can transform trees into tools and houses, fur into coats, claws into tools or decorations. The whole ecosystem is the diet of humanity.

Again, the same process happens at any level. For the transition $L_{0 \rightarrow 1}$, the RNA's targeted catalysis generated amino acids, nucleic acids, and other useful components from any organic compound it could find. For the transition $L_{1 \rightarrow 2}$, the DNA's targeted editing allowed to transform external DNA into useful strands, for example, through a precursor of CRISPR [25], [26] or horizontal gene transfer [27]. Species at levels L_3 and L_4 can digest the other species via phagocytosis and digestive tract and reduce most of their organic mass into simple sugars, lipids, or amino acids.

For the level L_6 , it is unknown how they will use nuclear bombs in a transformative rather than a destructive manner, but good guesses would be nuclear energy, transport, and terraforming planets [28]. Nuclear power is quite different from other PMDs since it is the only one that does not rely on organic chemistry but the mining of specific atoms (uranium and plutonium for fission or hydrogen for fusion). Hence, it will transform land and planets into hospitable areas instead of transforming living into useful components.

2.6 Domestication

As mentioned earlier, a strong increase in population size is fundamental to controlling the PMD and avoiding self-destruction. However, such an increase in population will necessarily cause the scarcity of food and resources. Hence, domestication comes as a natural way of increasing food supply by orders of magnitude.

Key ideas

Simply destroying other species wastes many resources. Instead, they must be transformed into energy or useful components.

Key ideas

As population size increases, the species transitioning to level L_{n+1} will domesticate other livings of level $L_{\leq n}$ to increase food and resource availability.

Here, *domestication* is defined as a form of imbalanced symbiosis, in the sense that one species dominates the other to gather its resources while providing shelter and basic resources for its needs. The dominated species will be slowly modified to be more resource-efficient while losing attributes that allow it to survive in the wild, eventually not being considered alive anymore. An example is the mitochondria: despite originating from a prokaryote, it is considered a non-alive organelle [7], [8] since they cannot survive outside the cell. Another example is how chickens are overgrown so much that they can no longer walk as adults and cannot survive in the wild. Eventually, chickens will not be live animals since they will be lab-grown [29]. The same will also apply to other livestock or agricultural plants.

Domestication can be viewed as a targeted control of the PMD used to protect and fertilize the species efficient at resource and energy gathering. During the transition $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$, the transitioning species uses its new PMD to provide shelter by destroying those that are a threat or compete with its resources. Further, the improved information power and ability to transfer resources allow fertilizing and feeding the domesticated species with far more resources than its typical food intake in the wild.

There is a noticeable difference between the domestication that happens at odd levels versus even levels. For odd levels $L_{1,3,5}$, the domesticated species is from the previous level. In contrast, even levels $L_{2,4,6}$ simply expand the scale of the domestication of the same species.

The life $L_{1,2}$ domesticated the ribosomes, a form of L_0 RNA-pseudo-life. Ribosomes comprise short RNA strands and proteins that specialize in decoding mRNA into proteins [30]. In general, ribosomal activity is limited by the number of amino and nucleic acids present in the wild, and ribosomes cannot self-reproduce. With the rise of the L_1 RNA life, domesticating the ribosome was essential to produce different proteins [31]. In prokaryotes, the scale of domestication increased, allowing the cells to produce various proteins. Note that, since L_1 could not survive outside of their natural habitat, they became forced parasites to L_2 [31] (see section 3.2.3) and therefore lost the ability to produce ribosomes.

For $L_{3,4}$ the mitochondria and chloroplast are optimally domesticated to the point that their function is limited; they cannot survive alone [7], [8]. This domestication is known as the endosymbiosis theory. With the protection of the eukaryotes, the lifespan of the symbiont increases significantly beyond the bacterial lifespan. The domestication of the mitochondria and chloroplast provides the L_3 species with a vast amount of energy. In L_4 , the domestication is at a much larger scale, as liver cells can have thousands of mitochondria, compared to the single mitochondrion found in most eukaryotes [32].

For $L_{5,6}$ the domestication is visible by the great changes to the ecosystem brought by farming, first at a small scale in L_5 with hunting dogs, a few cattle, and small farmlands, then in $L_{5 \rightarrow 6}$ with industrial farms, vertical farming, and lab-grown meat. Indeed,

Domestication

The definition of domestication is extended beyond humans. It applies to different life-forms where the same kind of imbalanced symbiosis is observed between the dominant life $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$ and dominated life $L_{\leq n}$.

today there are over 20 billion chickens globally [33], and that number keeps increasing.

2.7 Automated machines

Following the same ideas that sustained growth requires domestication of species to produce resources and energy efficiently, the proposed theory argues that automating major processes is also necessary. The automation helps expand the size of the species while ensuring that resources are consumed and shared efficiently across its members. In addition, automated machines help the locomotion of a given species and help to detect or avoid environmental threats.

Automation requires major structures and strong population sizes to be efficient and useful, meaning that they are mostly present at even levels $L_{2,4,6}$ although some basic machines are present at odd levels. Humans are used to thinking that they are the only species to create robots, factories, sensors, and automated transportation systems. This section shows that these same inventions happen at every even-numbered level and that they tend to resemble the species from the previous level, as is evident with the rise of human-like robots.

Also, note that with the increased population size, an immune system is required for protection. Hence, there is a refactoring of the 2 highest levels of PMD into an automated immune system that can identify and attack invaders.

At level L_2 , prokaryotes developed a wide variety of protein-based machines, the cytoskeleton to improve cell division [34] and the ion pump to produce ATP [2], [34]. They created multiple machines for protein folding and degradation, metabolosomes to carry reactions, and taxis to respond to environmental stimuli [34]. Most of these machines are similar to species of level L_1 as they are primarily composed of amino and nucleic acids. They also have their equivalent in human civilization, with ATP being similar to electricity/oil, proteins folding to factories, and taxis to satellite surveillance. Further, the targeted catalysis and editing are refactored into CRISPR or other immune responses.

At level L_4 , animals with full digestive tract automated multiple types of machinery thanks to the apparition of muscles and skeletons to allow complex movements. For one, the heart and the circulatory system improved during the Cambrian explosion [13], [35] and allowed spreading resources more efficiently across all cells. Further, different organs allow to increase the efficiency of the digestive system, and their function is automated using neural stimuli. These same neural stimuli allow animals to sense the environment and automate protective responses in case of threats. Further, some organs act as *factories* of proteins and other tissues. Note that an individual organ shares a similarity with L_3 species (lower animals and other eukaryotes). The phagocytosis and digestive enzymes are also refactored to act as the immune system.

At level L_6 , Planeta Hominis automated factories and agriculture thanks to robotics. Robots share many similarities to the Homo Sapiens of level L_5 , but with the only

Key ideas

The creation of automated machines is not unique to humans; it happens at every even level. The machines allow automating the processing/distribution of resources within a living, increasing locomotion, adding environmental sensors, and building an immune system.

purpose of working, producing, and distributing goods efficiently. Thanks to the construction of transportation systems, automated cars can deliver resources directly to each individual. In Planeta Hominis, the internet controls all actions by sending the appropriate instruction where needed, a role similar to the nervous system. Further, Planeta Hominis uses satellites and arrays of sensors to automate the responses to threats and changes in the environment. Finally, fire and nuclear energy will be refactored to produce automated weapons that act as immune systems.

2.8 Consciousness

Another important aspect of the proposed theory is the concept of different levels of consciousness, meaning that self-awareness improves with each level of life. This improved consciousness helps survive self-destruction from the PMD since it unites the behavior of all components of a given species towards a common goal and prevents self-harm. It is directly related to the improved information processing and the improved automation of the species.

In this section, consciousness is generalized to all species, in opposition to most theories that focus on the human or the animal mind. Even simple species like viruses and bacteria exhibit a primitive form of consciousness, while the L_6 civilizations exhibit a form of consciousness much more advanced than the human mind.

Although similar ideas exist, such as the Vedantic view of consciousness [36], a philosophical idea that considers that all matter is conscious, this work distances itself from their view. Philosophers always viewed consciousness as a hard question that science cannot answer [37], yet the proposed theory aims to provide a scientific answer. First, consciousness is only attributed to living things, not to all matter. Second, consciousness is considered to arise from a scientific evolutionary point of view as a means to avoid self-destruction.

On the lowest level L_1 , RNA strands exhibit an awareness of when and where to reproduce. For example, for viruses, there needs to be an event that triggers the genetic information to escape its protein shell; otherwise the virus is mostly dormant [38]. Due to the very fast degradation of RNA, this process allows them to stay alive long enough for reproduction.

At L_2 , prokaryotes can detect and react to threats in their environment. For example, they can enter dormancy to survive the presence of toxins, environmental changes, or a lack of resources [39], [40]. They can also detect the presence of infectious RNA and act against it using CRISPR, or the presence of beneficial DNA and integrate it through conjugation [41].

On the eukaryote level L_3 , a more advanced form of consciousness allows species to identify whether their neighbors are part of the colony and do apoptosis (cell suicide) if they are damaged or a threat to others [42]. Eukaryotes can also detect invaders and attack them but avoid attacking their own colonies. They can further understand or modify their role via epigenetics [43], [44].

Key ideas

Consciousness is generalized beyond the human mind to all living things. Viruses and bacteria exhibit a primitive form of consciousness to allow reproduction and survival, while Planeta Hominis have the most advanced form, allowing to track and optimize themselves and their components.

At L_4 , animals reach a greater awareness by sensing their environment and understanding their relative position in terms of time and space [45]. Thus, they can determine when and where to gather resources, avoid dangers, and improve their actions by learning from experience. This new level of consciousness allows animals to adapt to their environment, anticipate danger, and solve simple problems [45], [46].

On the human tribe level L_5 , humans extend their consciousness by being able to decide and change their behavior not only on immediate rewards but also from feedback, expected long-term rewards, and belief in a greater system (religion, traditions, philosophy). They can also understand the role of others (priest, healer, hunter) and follow leaders.

Finally, the level 6 civilizations L_6 exhibit the highest level of consciousness as it is not only aware of the humans that compose the civilization but can track, predict, and optimize their movements, their habits, and their decisions. They further understand how life works and can track all its components using sensors, from organ functions to cell damage to DNA diseases, providing a much deeper self-awareness than simple humans. They make use of ethics and other abstract constructs to ensure cohesive behavior beyond the spirituality of L_5 . Although the transition is not yet complete, the best examples are mega-corporations such as Google and mega-governments like the United States and Chinese governments.

2.9 After the transition: Back to the equilibrium

Destroying other species and breaking the equilibrium is fundamental to transitioning to a new level. However, it would be wrong to assume that the new level will continue to dominate, destroy and consume all other species. After the transition is complete, there is a new equilibrium where the high-level species become part of a new ecosystem.

For example, the animal digestive and immune system destroy most lower-level life, such as viruses, bacteria, and fungi, but infections from lower-level viruses and bacteria may kill the animal host. Further, not all lower species are parasitic. Many are beneficial to the higher species either through symbiosis or by contributing to the ecosystem.

Returning to equilibrium is fundamental for all life since it acts as a population and resource control for the new species. It also highlights how death is as important as reproduction in any functional ecosystem [47], [48].

2.10 Section summary

Key ideas

After the transition is complete, the use of the PMD calms down. A new equilibrium is reached where the living at the higher level stops destroying and consuming everything. They can be killed by lower-level life or form symbiosis.

Table 2: Detailed summary of the characteristics of all levels of life. The rows about “*perception of time*” and “*ecosystem energy*” are discussed in later sections.

	LEVEL 0 L_0	LEVEL 1 L_1	LEVEL 2 L_2	LEVEL 3 L_3	LEVEL 4 L_4	LEVEL 5 L_5	LEVEL 6 L_6
Event Living at this level	Chemical soup • Small organic molecules • Amino and nucleic acids • Small RNA and protein complexes without defined functionality	RNA life and viruses • RNA viruses • Pre-bacterial cells	Origin of cellular life • Prokaryotes o Bacteria o Archaea	Origin of complex life • Eukaryotes o Protists o Fungi o Algae o Animals without a full digestive tract	Cambrian explosion • Animals with full digestive tracts	Homo Sapiens tribes • Tribes and kingdoms of Homo	Inter-planetary civilization • Planeta Hominis
Power of mass destruction (PMD) Power to selectively destroy entire colonies of other colonies without self-harm	-	Targeted catalysis Transforms simple molecules into RNA/protein building blocks. PMD is used to produce RNA or useful proteins.	Targeted editing Modify DNA and insert its DNA into other species. PMD is used to hijack foreign mechanisms into producing and protecting the inserted DNA.	Phagocytosis Dismantle bacteria without cross infecting the genome. PMD is used to feed the eukaryote and provide nutrients.	Digestive tract Dismantle Eukaryotic colonies. PMD is used to feed the animal and provide nutrients.	Fire Dismantle animals and forests. Build tools with dead remnants. PMD increases digestion speed and nutrients consumption, clear territory, build tools, and machinery.	Nuclear bomb+ Dismantle cities and states. <i>This power is not yet mastered.</i> PMD is used to generate energy, terraform planets, build interplanetary tools, and machinery.
Information power New abilities of processing and exchanging information <i>Pre-requisite to control the PMD.</i> <i>Improves PMD co-evolution.</i> <i>command: equivalent command or function in a programming language</i>	-	RNA Write and execute commands with RNA and Ribosome write/run [Post-PMD] Production of enzymes for reproduction copy	DNA functions Load functions from DNA, execute with mRNA, and stop with Riboswitch load, function, stop [Post-PMD] Locate specific sequences, share them with horizontal gene transfer, delete them with CRISPR, or correct errors find, share, delete, edit	Epigenetics Conditional and weighted functions using epigenome if, switch, multiply [Post-PMD] Store information in a secured location and import them when needed Archive, import	Neurons Wait for input or event wait, event handler [Post-PMD] Understand and predict the behavior of others, repeat and learn to optimize their behavior while, fit, train	Language Speak, make stories, discuss, transfer learning and teach teach [Post-PMD] Repeat action with the expectation of reward, but no immediate reward learn [Post-PMD] Transaction and exchanges between resources, money count, trade	Computing Accounting, transactions using numerical currencies, and credit evaluate, buy, sell, hold Mathematical modeling and prediction of the physical world predict [Post-PMD] Parallel computing, light-speed numerical communication (internet) thread, q-bit, sync, download
Resistance to self-destruction Development of processes to avoid destroying each other in perpetual wars <i>Co-evolves with the PMD</i>	-	Protective membrane Build protein and simple lipid membrane Some viruses use DNA as a more stable version of RNA.	CRISPR, corrective editing Can identify and eliminate invading DNA (with CRISPR) and correct errors (with RecA, RadA). Restriction enzymes allow controlling which DNA strand gets included.	Sexual reproduction Avoids wars between early eukaryotic colonies by introducing a means of <i>cooperative reproduction</i> . Notice how humans also used sexual reproduction to unite kingdoms and avoid wars.	Membranes and Skeletons Isolate the digestion from the rest of the body through a membrane, where bacteria are farmed to digest complex molecules. Exoskeletons make it harder to consume one another and allow better movement to evade prey.	Spirituality Create a sense of belonging, of <i>us VS them</i> , with strong cooperation. Create rituals so that destructive actions are meaningful, with an awareness of its dangers.	Globalization Wealth and resources become interdependent in every part of the world. Currencies, languages, and ethics become unified. Awareness of the dangers of nuclear energy.
Consciousness Consciousness is generalized to all living things <i>Co-evolves with the PMD</i>	-	Start reproduction • Knows when and where to reproduce	Detect threats • Knows about the resources and threats in their environment • Can identify foreign DNA.	Identify neighbors • Knows about the presence of other species and can identify them. • Knows their role and behavior and control their genetic expression	Sense the environment • Understands its position (time and space) relative to its surroundings • Learns from experience • Knows when and where to gather resources	Decide and adjust role • Decide and change its role and behavior based on feedback/reward/belief • Knows its constituents and roles (hunter, priest, healer, ...) • Select and reject leaders	Understand and optimize itself • Knows its constituents at every level (cells, organs, cities, ...) • Can track, predict and optimize the behavior of its constituents • Knows how life works and how to maximize resources from other livings • Uses ethics to define acceptable actions
Domestication Protect resource-rich species while controlling their life cycles <i>Appears at every odd level to maximize resources.</i>	-	Ribosomes Ribosomes are complexes composed of rRNA and small proteins. They are farmed to produce proteins from amino acids. The remaining virus species lost the ribosome since they became obligated parasites.	None Improved production of amino acids.	Mitochondria and chloroplast Mitochondria and chloroplasts were previously bacteria. They are acquired and farmed inside the cell to maximize resource production.	None Thousands of mitochondria can exist in a single cell and bacterial farming in the intestine.	Dogs, cattle, farmland Animals are domesticated to improve hunting and increase food supply. Plants such as wheat and rice are farmed.	None Improved land and animal farming with 3D farms and lab-grown meat.
Automation The development of automated machines to increase efficiency. <i>Appears at every even level to maximize expansion</i>	-	-	Proteins Proteins are used to regulate processes (metabolosomes), transfer ATP ions through the membrane (ion transporter), transmit messages, etc.	-	Resource transport Automate transport of nutrients and oxygen in the blood. Regulate PH, salt levels, and temperature.	-	Robotics Automated factories and trucks to generate and distribute resources, and automated data collection and analysis.
Perception of time The way that time and decisions are perceived	Quantum Time flows in a quantum/non-deterministic way. Decisions are stochastic.	Quantum	Quantum	Linear Time flows linearly, decisions are causal, and there is enough redundancy to avoid randomness. The cycle of life is timed with the cycles of days and seasons.	Linear	Linear	Space-time The decisions must consider the theory of relativity for energy, resource transfer, and reproduction.
Ecosystem energy The type of energy that fuels the ecosystem	Thermal Thermal and chemical energy from nearby heat sources and chemical sources.	Thermal	Thermal Some species develop solar energy, such as cyanobacteria. However, most species still rely on thermal energy.	Solar Species rely on solar energy to feed plankton, algae, and plants. In return, they feed the whole ecosystem.	Solar	Solar Fire mostly uses wood, which relies on solar energy.	Nuclear Species rely on nuclear fission, fusion, and energy extraction from the stars to feed the ecosystems.

3 Fractal life

An important aspect of this theory is that life is categorized into 6 different and discrete levels, with the transition between each level happening quickly after acquiring a PMD. As explained in the previous section, a level increase implies a population increase, a higher information processing power, and the improvement of domestication or automation.

In the proposed theory, the level L_0 represents the soup of organic chemicals that is necessary for the first RNA-based species to emerge. Levels are also categorized as being *odd*-numbered or *even*-numbered to highlight the similarities between levels $L_{1,3,5}$ which give rise to domestication and a collaborative population; compared to levels $L_{2,4,6}$ with a stronger collaboration via hyper-specialization, automation, and a loss of independence from its sub-individuals.

The current section will overview the different levels of life, their characteristics, and how they evolved. Most of the ideas are summarized in Figure 4, showing the transition timeline between levels that starts with the control of a PMD.

In short, life L_{n+1} first starts appearing after it controls a new power of mass destruction (PMD) since it allows it to destroy or dominate any life L_n . This PMD co-evolves with a new information processing power that allows the life $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$ to destroy competing species while avoiding self-destruction. Resisting self-destruction also brings a new structure, a bigger population, the rise of domestication, automation, and greater consciousness. The process is a fractal since a life L_n is a sub-component of life L_{n+1} with significant self-similarities.

Key ideas

Fractals are used to model the structure of life as levels of self-contained ecosystems with strong self-similarities: civilizations made of cities, cities made of humans, humans made of cells, cells made of DNA and RNA. Further, all levels originate from similar steps with a strong self-similarity every 2 levels.

Figure 4. A possible timeline of the transition between levels. The level transition starts at step c) with the acquisition of the PMD and is followed by a great improvement in the efficacy of the PMD, the information power, the consciousness, and the population size in steps d-e-f). The transition from c) to f) is expected to be very fast in evolutionary terms, usually taking less than a million years. However, the transition from a) to b) happens in many species, and it can take tens of millions of years before one species goes to step c), so the transition starts at step c).

3.1 Odd and Even levels

As apparent in Figure 4's coloring, the different levels are categorized as being *odd* or *even*. This separation highlights the similarities shared by odd levels $L_{1,3,5}$, which are colony-like species with simple structures and domestication. In contrast, even levels $L_{2,4,6}$ are more deeply integrated within their colonies, have over-specialization and automation. In addition, natural selection and group selection behave differently for odd and even levels.

3.1.1 Odd levels $L_{1,3,5}$

Despite the large difference in their complexity, odd levels species (viruses, eukaryotes, and homo sapiens) share multiple similarities. In general, odd-level species consume the same kind of resources as their previous level, although at a much larger scale and using domestication. They form complex and large colonies, but they are not enclosed. Some individuals can move between them and start new colonies by themselves.

In early versions of the proposed theory, odd levels were considered transition steps between the even levels. This view aligns with the traditional view of biology that considers viruses as not alive, eukaryotes as more complex bacteria, and homo sapiens as animals. However, we decided to classify them as different levels since they are significantly more complex and possess a more advanced PMD, information processing, consciousness, and complexity; and since they experience group selection.

Natural selection slows down for the individual L_{n-1} that forms the colony since the appurtenance to a group and the possession of a PMD protect them. Instead, natural selection happens partially at the individual level L_{n-1} and partially at the colony level L_n (partial group selection). In fact, the genetic code's mutation rate, which can measure natural selection for individuals, is far lower for higher levels [49].

3.1.2 Even levels $L_{2,4,6}$

Even-numbered species, i.e., prokaryotes, animals with the digestive tract, and Planeta Hominis, represent a much stronger step in the evolution of life, as they behave completely differently from previous levels. For example, bacteria can move and reproduce by themselves, animals with the digestive tract can process stimuli and think, while Planeta Hominis can compute and travel across planets.

Even levels are characterized by the development of a PMD that is a larger-scale version of the PMD from its previous level. Indeed, targeted editing is a larger equivalent of targeted catalysis, digestion is a larger equivalent of phagocytosis, and nuclear energy is a larger equivalent of fire. They are formed by species 2 levels lower, i.e. L_{n-2} . They can be interpreted as a consolidated colony that acts as a whole and where the identity of the individuals composing it (levels L_{n-2}) is lost.

Key ideas

Odd levels $L_{1,3,5}$ are small colonies formed by previous level species, but with an acquired PMD and more complex social structure than typical colonies.

Key ideas

Even levels $L_{2,4,6}$ are very large colonies formed by species 2 levels lower L_{n-2} , but possess 2 new levels of PMD. They are very different from lower levels, consume different resources, occupy different environments, and have a highly complex social structure with over-specialization.

To deal with its vast increase in size and complexity, it develops automated processes and machines that improve its efficiency to produce and share resources and components across its social structure.

Natural selection practically stops for the individuals L_{n-2} inside the even level and only applies to the whole, it becomes a complete *group selection*. For example, most humans within a society survive even if they would have died in the wild, meaning that natural selection no longer drives the gene pool within a society. The same is true for cells in an animal and individual genome within bacteria.

This stop in natural selection is necessary for the extreme specialization that happens to the individuals within the even levels. Extreme specialization is necessary to increase the new species' complexity, leading to individuals that cannot survive in the wild. For example, at L_2 most genomes are useless as individuals, such as the non-coding *junk* DNA that are helpful at gene regularization, a process that does not exist outside the bacterial host [50], [51]. At L_4 cells are only useful within their organs and won't survive if separated from their body [52]. And at L_6 , humans will have genetic code and knowledge set that is very specific to their task and will not be able to survive outside of civilization.

Even levels also act as a vessel for other species. Since their way of life changes completely and their resource requirement grows massively, even level species can move between territories more efficiently and cross boundaries inaccessible to other species. For instance, prokaryotes can escape hydrothermal vents and carry viruses and chemical ingredients with them. Animals can cross oceans and deserts and carry seeds, prokaryotes, and viruses with them. Moreover, *Planeta Hominis* can travel between planets, carrying all lower-level living with them.

3.1.3 Group selection

Group selection is the notion that natural selection can also occur at the level of the group, not only at the individual, meaning that natural selection rewards cooperation in the long term. It is a highly debated theory, with many biologists arguing against the idea for the past decades partly due to the failure of mathematical models [53], [54] except for the rare cases of eusociality [55]. Despite still being the subject of debates, the theory is recently gaining more traction thanks to the success of recent mathematical models [56], [57].

However, biologists arguing against group selection make a simple yet major mistake in their reasoning: when considering an animal or plant as a single living that experiences natural selection, in reality, they are looking at a group of eukaryotes. They are simply changing the definition of "individual" to fit their view that evolution only happens at the individual level. The fractal nature of life means that individuals do not exist; an individual is simply an ecosystem of lower-level species.

As mentioned in the previous sections, group selection is the dominant form of selection for even-level species, meaning that prokaryotes, animals, and *Planeta*

Key ideas

There is no such thing as an "individual" in biology, each species is a group of smaller livings. Thus, natural selection only applies to groups. For even levels, natural selection mostly happens to the highest-level group, whether for odd levels, it happens at the highest 2 levels at once.

Hominis are considered “individuals” in the traditional sense of evolutionary theory. For odd-level species, there is a balance between individual and group selection. Some species exhibit mostly group selection (plants, algae), while others exhibit mostly individual selection (some protists).

3.1.4 Studying natural selection from the information powers

Rather than studying natural selection from the evolution of the genome, it becomes more appropriate to study it from the evolution of all levels of information powers. Indeed, the epigenome is important in the study of eukaryotes [58], [59], and human diseases [60]. Further, knowledge and communication are important in animals and can be shared across generations, giving an advantage to certain groups of the same species [61]. Finally, culture and language in homo sapiens are also studied from a natural selection point of view [20], [62].

Hence, DNA changes become less relevant in explaining the diversity of physical traits and behaviors in higher-level species. Instead, all levels of information power must be taken into account.

3.2 Origin of life: Levels L_0, L_1, L_2

This section discusses the origin of life, how RNA life emerged from the Primordial soup, and how it led to prokaryotes. With most details already given in Table 2 and Figure 4, the following paragraphs will be short and explain how this theory positions itself relative to other theories on the origin of life.

3.2.1 L_0 : Primordial soup

Many theories are related to how the Earth was before life emerged and how it provided multiple ingredients that would yield to the origin of life. One such theory is that life emerged from a chemical soup of organic matter, where the building blocks were available in large amounts. This theory claims that the chemical soup was created by physical processes such as volcanic activities and lightning [2]. Recently, the theory that life emerged from hydrothermal vents gained popularity since the vents can provide energy, large amounts of chemicals, and possess porous surfaces to catalyze reactions [2], [63].

However, neither theory provide a clear mechanism for how life emerged. The proposed fractal-life theory does not oppose nor support any of these theories regarding where the origin of life happened; it simply provides a mechanism by which life could have started when simple RNA started to catalyze useful reactions.

3.2.2 L_1 : RNA life

The proposed theory splits the *traditional* origin of life into 2 distinct steps. The first step is the emergence of RNA-based life L_1 and the second step is the emergence of prokaryotes L_2 . Note that this theory directly supports the “RNA-world” theory on the

Key ideas

DNA changes become less relevant in explaining the diversity of higher-level species. Instead, all levels of information powers must be studied to grasp a systems’ behavior fully.

Key ideas

The proposed theory aligns well with the prominent theory of *RNA world*. It further provides a mechanism for both the formation of the *RNA world* at L_1 and the origin of life at L_2 .

Panspermia

Panspermia hypothesizes that life exists all over spaces, in dust clouds, comets, and different planets. It implies that life on Earth originated elsewhere in the galaxy. The proposed work does not deny or confirm the panspermia theory. Rather, it suggests a mechanism that led to the formation of life, whether it was on Earth or in Space.

origin of life, one of the leading theories which state that simple RNA species populated the Earth before the emergence of DNA species and bacteria [3], [31].

This work argues that, due to the destructive nature of the origin, the rise of RNA life L_1 likely happened at one specific location (see section 4.1). Using its ability to catalyze reactions, the L_1 were able to build protein and lipid membranes to propagate outside of their native habitat and populate other regions of similar physicochemical properties. Again, this aligns with recent findings that the ability of RNA to catalyze reactions could be the key to the origin of life [18].

3.2.3 L_2 : Prokaryotes

The theory also does not oppose nor support the different theories about primordial soups and hydrothermal vents for the origin of prokaryotes. Again, it argues that the origin of prokaryotes likely happened at a single location, supporting prominent theories [2], [64], with the DNA acquiring the power to target and modify RNA and DNA selectively. Hence, bacteria and archaea share a common ancestor, and they split into two branches during the transition $L_{1 \rightarrow 2}$.

Prokaryotes' ability to control their metabolism and regulate their internal environment allowed them to spread throughout the planet and survive in different environments. They further enabled parasitic viruses to spread more and survive in environments different than their native region, which explains why most L_1 species became obligated parasites [31].

3.3 Origin of complex life: Levels L_3, L_4

This section discusses the origin of complex life, how eukaryotes emerged from prokaryotes, and how it led to the rise of complex animals. With most details already given in Table 2 and Figure 4, the following paragraphs will be short and position the theory relative to other theories on the origin of complex life.

3.3.1 L_3 : Eukaryotes

Endosymbiosis is the prominent theory for the emergence of eukaryotes. It states that through phagocytosis, an Archaea acquired a bacterium without killing it. This acquisition led to a very efficient symbiosis where the bacteria later evolved into mitochondria and the archaea evolved into a host cell, allowing the host to grow much larger and more complex [2], [7], [8].

Endosymbiosis aligns perfectly with the presented theory: phagocytosis is the PMD, and mitochondria are the domesticated species. This work further explains how the acquisition of the phagocytosis allowed the eukaryotes L_3 to become more complex than prokaryotes L_2 , have longer DNA with epigenetics, and live in larger colonies. Natural selection makes it difficult to explain this large difference between eukaryotes and prokaryotes since it relies on slow and steady changes and expects to find transition species.

Key ideas

The proposed theory aligns well with the prominent *endosymbiotic* theory for the origin of eukaryotic cells L_3 , and provides a rationale for the *Cambrian explosion* that followed the apparition of L_4 .

Regarding the presence of sexual reproduction in eukaryotes, we believe that it arose as a strategy to avoid war between colonies and force collaborations. Human tribes and kingdoms used the same strategy for thousands of years: marrying a prince and princess from different kingdoms as a peace treaty is a form of L_5 sexual reproduction.

3.3.2 L_4 : Animals with a full digestive tract

The origin of animals is not an open question in biology since there is a smooth transition between multiple species, ranging from simple sponges 800 million years ago and diversifying greatly during the Ediacaran period 653 million years ago. However, there is a major change in the fossil record 541 million years ago during the Cambrian explosion, an event not fully understood. There are multiple hypotheses about what happened to trigger such an event, with each theory focusing on a few elements. Examples are the changes in feeding, the apparition of the exoskeleton, the increase in oxygen, the evolution of the eyes, or the arms race between predator and prey [13], [19], [35], [65].

From the point of view of the proposed theory, the Cambrian explosion has a simple explanation: developing a full digestive tract that allowed animals to destroy other species and consume them quickly. This digestive system contrasts heavily with the filtering feeding from sponges and mouth-only feeding from jellyfish and the urbilaterian [19] that are very slow and non-targeted.

After the apparition of a full digestive system, the transitioning life $L_{3 \rightarrow 4}$ started to consume other L_3 species massively and led to heavy competition in resources. This competition naturally gave rise to the evolution of eyes and other sensory organs (improved information level) and exoskeletons (resistance to PMD). Hence, this theory is not compatible with any **single** hypothesis for the Cambrian explosion. Instead, it gives a mechanism for the rise of a level L_4 via the acquisition of a PMD that is compatible with the Cambrian explosion. It suggests that multiple proposed hypotheses happened in co-evolution to the PMD (change in feeding, predatory arms race, improved neural system, and the apparition of eyes). All these elements were necessary both to control the PMD and avoid self-destruction.

3.4 Origin of human civilization: Levels L_5, L_6

With most details already given in Table 2 and Figure 4, the following paragraphs will be short and position the theory relative to other theories on the origin of human civilization.

3.4.1 L_5 : Homo Sapiens

Traditionally, the history of human civilization is viewed as the evolution of a species with superior intelligence that dominated the Earth thanks to its ability to create and use tools [20], [21]. However, this section argues that the key element that defined the evolution of human civilization is not its ability to build but its ability to destroy all

Key ideas

The proposed theory aligns well with the theory that fire is the main factor for human evolution and with the nuclear peace theory. All other characteristics of humans (intelligence, toolmaking, social skills, communication, imagination) simply co-evolved with fire or nuclear energy.

other species with fire. Superior intelligence, language, and consciousness were simply a necessary co-evolution of fire.

There are multiple animals such as chimpanzees, elephants, crows, and octopuses with high intelligence and the ability to use tools. Some of these species also communicate and share knowledge across generations, just like humans. Nevertheless, they have not built civilizations. Further, eusocial animals such as ants, bees, and naked mole-rats have complex social structures yet have not built civilizations and empires to dominate the Earth.

Instead, the presented theory on the origin of civilization aligns perfectly with other theories that claim that the control of fire was the pivoting step in the evolution of the homo genus [16], [20], [23], [66]. It implies that the control of fire was the central step and, as it improved, social structure and intelligence co-improved. Thus, homo sapiens were able to overtake the world and exterminate competing homo genus. Farming and domestication were necessary for increasing food supply and avoid starvation from population expansion.

Myths, legends, religion, and philosophy evolved to transmit knowledge and wisdom across generations, with their main purpose being to better control fire and avoid self-destruction. Indeed, there are multiple myths about humans teaming to fight a common enemy, about spirits/natural disasters attacking humans for their greed and for destroying the environment, and about the dangers of human inventions. Religion and spirituality forced humans to have rituals around fire and hunting and create political systems and rules to prevent abuse of their PMD.

In addition, the presented theory suggests that there is a noticeable slow-down in the evolution of individual humans as social structures protect them. Instead, natural selection applies partially to the groups. Group traits, such as culture, warfare, political systems, religion, and language, evolve to become more efficient and more likely to survive and propagate. However, individual human evolution still happens partially at L_5 with a balance between group selection and individual selection [54].

It is thought that the homo genus first interacted with fire about 1.5M years ago, which represents the start of the transition $L_{4 \rightarrow 5}$. Around 400k years ago, the homo genus started to use fire more regularly and integrate it into their daily lives. This primitive control of the fire PMD led to a very fast evolution of the homo genus until the transition to L_5 was complete around 100k years ago with the modern homo sapiens [23], [24].

3.4.2 L_6 : Planeta Hominis

This theory splits the history of human civilization into 2 parts, the first part starting with the control of fire and the second part with the control of nuclear energy. With the development of nuclear weapons and energy, human civilization gained the ability to terraform planets and navigate between them.

However, humans can also self-annihilate if the nations decide to use their nuclear weapons freely. Since the size of the planet is too small for multiple L_6 species, then the natural way of surviving is through heavy globalization; by creating a global economy and structure, all nations lose by using their nuclear weapons. This concept is known as the *nuclear peace* theory [20], [67] and aligns perfectly with the presented theory.

We hypothesize that, in the short future (hundreds of years), the planet will be ruled by a single government, and that government will become a species of level L_6 with sub-government and industries having similar functions to organs. Humans will become over-specialized and fully dependant on the system, the same way that a cell in an animal body can only achieve specific functions and cannot survive without the full body providing nutrients. There are many features of L_6 that we can find analogs in L_4 such as the blood and lymphatic system (cargo trains and boats, home delivery, police patrols), the nervous system (internet), and the brain (government, artificial intelligence, search engines).

Then, in a few million years, there will be thousands of colonized planets. There will be different species of *Planeta Hominis*, each with its own culture and its own species of human. Some will specialize in extracting energy from the surface of planets, others in extracting solar energy, others in extracting the core of planets. There will be scavenger species, looking at extracting the remnants of a dead civilization, and hunter species, destroying inhabited planets and extracting its resources.

War will no longer be between tribes; it will be between planets. And there will not be empires as depicted in science fiction such as *Star Wars*. Each planet will have its own rule, with its desire to survive, to reproduce, and its own form of consciousness. Governments will likely become decentralized, meaning that there will not be a single human acting as president; rather, there will be an algorithm taking into account the needs of the individuals and the whole.

For the L_6 species, the nuclear bomb PMD will be repurposed to terraform planets/asteroids by reshaping their surfaces, digging holes, or heating specific regions. Nuclear fusion and fission will provide energy to sustain different *Planeta Hominis* species across the galaxy.

In addition, nuclear bombs will also be used by *hunter* species of *Planeta Hominis* to attack and *eat* the energy-rich *prey* species. One can imagine the *prey* species as a larger scale analog to plants. They will be huge producers of nuclear fusion energy, using it to dig rare minerals in the planetary core and stores the excess energy into nuclear batteries, similar to how plants dig minerals and store solar energy in the form of glucose. They will reproduce quickly and spread across the galaxy, and a major part of the galactic ecosystem will feed on them.

3.5 Future of life: Levels L_7 , L_8 (Speculation)

This section presents some hypotheses and thought experiments about the future of life in tens of millions of years when the Planeta Hominis species would have spread through the nearest galaxies, and one species will have transitioned to L_7 or L_8 .

This section is speculative and does not try to predict the future accurately but rather to give an educated guess by extrapolating the current theory to new levels of life. Asking humans to understand the abilities of an L_8 species is analogous to asking a bacteria to describe the moon landing.

Although some concepts regarding the $L_{6,7,8}$ species are similar to the Kardashev scale of civilization [68], there are fundamental differences. Indeed, this work defines the levels by their destructive power, not their energy consumption, although they are correlated. Levels L_8 are also considered as a single living composed of millions of collaborative civilizations, not as a single advanced civilization.

3.5.1 L_7 : Gravity benders

As is the case with other levels of life, the transition to a new level starts with acquiring a new PMD over L_6 which can only be controlled by first acquiring a new level of information processing.

Level L_6 are planet-sized species, moving at a fraction of the speed of light and transferring information at the speed of light. To control a PMD over them, a *tribe* of ~ 100 Planeta Hominis must first communicate faster than light to synchronize the behavior of multiple planets properly. We hypothesize that multiple L_6 species that will be able to bend the fabric of space-time and create black holes, wormholes, or other unknown structures. The transitioning species $L_{6 \rightarrow 7}$ will use this same ability to bend space-time to create gravitational wells and catapults that can bend, destroy, or catapult planets and stars. Thus, they will be able to trap a solar system nearby in an unescapable well, shred it, and consume all its resources quickly and with no resistance.

The final L_7 species will be a tribe or kingdom of multiple Planeta Hominis moving together faster than light across a given galaxy and destroying solar systems along the way.

3.5.2 L_8 : Black hole benders

A species at the level L_8 becomes much more inconceivable for the human mind. We believe they will have a greater ability to bend space-time and destroy multiple stars simultaneously or even a large fraction of a galaxy into gigantic black holes. They will transfer information across time to the future and the past: they will become *a-temporal* beings that can reason outside causality. It is not easy to imagine what resources they will consume, how they will reproduce, or whether they will live in the observable space or within black holes. More details about the meaning of *a-temporal beings* are given in section 4.7.3.

Key ideas

Based on the proposed theory, it is possible to form educated guesses on the future of life, namely L_7 and L_8 .

L_7 can transfer information and resources faster than light and move or bend gravity to destroy planets and stars.

L_8 can live both in the past and future and can destroy entire galaxies by bending black holes.

4 Implications of the theory

Previous sections presented the different aspects of the theory, the elements necessary to transition between levels, and described each level. This section will present different implications of the given theory, summarized below.

4.1 First in, last in. Once a species reaches the level L_n , no other species within the occupied region will reach the same level. It is both the first and last to reach L_n .

4.2 The lack of intermediate species. There is no evidence of intermediate species between levels because the transition state is unstable. The first species to finish transitioning to L_n will outcompete any other transitioning living, even if they are closely related.

4.3 Reverse transition. Some species lose complexity; others even lose their PMD and transition in reverse $L_{n \rightarrow n-1}$.

4.4 Ants, bees, and eusocial animals. Despite having advanced social structures, eusocial animals are not at a higher level since they do not control a PMD. Thus, they must still adapt to their environment.

4.5 Amortality. The lifespan of the living L_{n-2} composing a higher-level organism L_n is significantly higher than wild species of level L_{n-2} . The same will be true for humans as they approach Amortality.

4.6 Fast transition to L_6 ? The transition $L_{5 \rightarrow 6}$ is happening shortly after $L_{4 \rightarrow 5}$. This can be attributed to the strong competition between L_5 civilisations due to the small relative size of the planet.

4.7 The perception of time. Time is perceived differently at each level. Lower levels $L_{0,1,2}$ experiment the quantum randomness of time, middle levels $L_{3,4,5}$ experiment time in a linear fashion, while higher levels $L_{6,7,8}$ experiment the space-time continuum.

4.8 Ecosystem energy. The sources of energy also vary across levels. Lower levels $L_{0,1,2}$ use heat and chemical energy, middle levels $L_{3,4,5}$ use solar energy, while higher levels $L_{6,7,8}$ use nuclear energy.

4.9 Validating the theory. What are the most important predictions, and how to validate them in the lab or computer simulations?

4.10 Destroying the Universe. Is the purpose of life to destroy the Universe and consume all its resources?

4.11 A new definition of life. A new definition of life is proposed, which is more rigorous and general than previous definitions.

4.1 First in, last in

One of the major implications of the proposed theory is that if a species reaches level L_n , it will be the only species to reach it. Thus, convergent evolution will not happen despite the PMD giving a major advantage to the concerned species. This implication directly opposes the standard Darwinism view of evolution but corresponds to empirical observations since all observed levels of life seem to have happened once [2], [64].

First, the transition between levels is due to acquiring a PMD that allows dominating every species in the ecosystem. Second, controlling a PMD can only happen if there are many resources to consume and large territory to expand. Thus, any species of level L_{n-1} that starts the transition to level L_n will not only be vastly outcompeted by another species at this level, but its newly acquired PMD will be no match against a fully transitioned L_n , thus it will never dominate the ecosystem.

Even considering the very unlikely scenario that two unrelated species independently acquire a PMD simultaneously, the species with the most destructive PMD will dominate and cause the extinction of the other. Think about how homo sapiens caused the extinction of all other species of the homo genus, despite being closely related and arriving millions of years later.

As a thought experiment, consider what would happen if humans found a new tribe of apes in the forest that starts controlling fire and building advanced tools. They would either be killed voluntarily, put into a zoo, or die via loss of habitat. Even if we decide to leave them in peace, they will never expand and dominate the planet since we are already there. They will be stuck in their restricted territory and eventually lose their ability to control fire since it will not provide any advantage: it will bring destruction without increasing their territory or resources.

The only way that 2 different species reach L_n is if they are out of reach from each other, for example, the apparition of bacterial life or animals on Earth does not mean that another planet will not host another form of L_2 or L_4 life, since bacteria and animals cannot travel across planets.

Hence, it is extremely unlikely that there is another L_6 species, commonly called an *intelligent species*, in the reachable galaxy. If there is one, then either it is reaching the level L_6 at the same time as humans and the most powerful will control the galaxy, or they are already here and will annihilate humans soon. However, we consider the latter to be very unlikely since an L_6 life will have a strong and observable energy output, constantly terraforming planets. Such changes remain unobserved in the galaxy, although current observational tools are limited.

Key ideas

Once a species reaches a level L_n , it becomes impossible for any other species to do the same transition within the occupied region, since it will be heavily outcompeted in terms of PMD control, resources, and territory.

4.2 The lack of intermediate species

On a related note, a mystery in the origin of life and complex life is the absence of intermediate species between levels [69], [70]. There are no half-virus/half-prokaryote to support the RNA-world theory. There are no half-prokaryote/half-eukaryote to support the endosymbiotic theory. And there are no homo genus other than homo sapiens (except in fossil records) [66].

This lack of intermediate species directly contradicts the standard theory of evolution. Standard evolutionary theory states that changes happen slowly and over a long period and almost guarantee the existence of intermediate species [69]. Further, it also almost guarantees that if the origin of a complex species or prokaryotes happened once, it should happen again in an unrelated species due to convergent evolution. However, all evidence point towards a single event for the origin of life [2], [64], eukaryotes [2], and complex animals [71].

The lack of intermediate forms has a simple explanation in the proposed theory, with similar ideas to section “4.1 First in, last in”.

First, the transition between levels happens very quickly on an evolutionary scale, leaving little time for intermediate species. Second, the first one to reach an advanced control of the PMD will likely wipe out all the others by either using the PMD or out-competing them for resources. Lastly, the fast expansion of the new level means that, with the limited resources and territory, the species that survives in the long term needs to dramatically improve its information processing, consciousness, societal structure, and automation. The *intermediate* transition state is unstable in the long term.

4.3 Reverse transition

Transitional species $L_{n \rightarrow n+1}$ are missing due to being in an unstable state. However, some species lose their PMD and transition in the reverse direction $L_{n \rightarrow n-1}$. Although the loss of a PMD can seem strange, trait reversal is typical in many species. For instance, many birds, such as penguins, lost their ability to fly.

Not all traits are lost during the reverse transition $L_{n \rightarrow n-1}$: the reversing species share characteristics of 2 different levels. For instance, giant viruses such as the mimivirus resemble both viruses and prokaryotes [72] but should be classified as L_1 . Sea cucumbers or individual protists such as amoeba lost much of their complexities without losing the PMDs, thus they did not transition in reverse and are respectively classified as L_4 and L_3 . The full study of these reversals is out of our current scope.

Key ideas

The proposed theory easily explains the lack of intermediate species and that the origin of life and complex life only happened once. Both these points cannot be explained by standard evolutionary theories such as natural selection.

Key ideas

Some species can lose part of their complexities over time. They can also lose their PMD via a reverse transition $L_{n \rightarrow n-1}$.

4.4 Ants, bees, and eusocial animals

Eusocial animals live in highly organized societies, with labor division, cooperative brood care, and separation into reproductive and non-reproductive groups. The best-known examples are ants and bees, but it is also present in rodents (naked mole-rat) and crustaceans (*Synalpheus regalis*) [73]. Scientists debate whether humans are also eusocial animals since they share multiple characteristics, including practices such as war, agriculture, and division of labor [74]. Some eusocial animals like bees and ants are so successful that they are found almost everywhere on Earth and are integral to ecosystems.

A question that arises is: why didn't any of these animal species dominated the Earth despite having advanced societies and distribution of labor for millions of years?

The current theory answers this question by the simple fact that none of these species controlled a PMD over other animals. Hence, even with an improved social structure, they did not pass to the next level and could not assert any form of domination over other species. They were constrained to adapt to their environment instead of adapting their environment to them.

Hence, it is not the societal structure that differentiates humans from other animals. The difference comes from humans' ability to dominate other species and bend the environment to their will via the PMD.

4.5 Amortality

At each new level of life, the increase in population size, complexity, and self-control ensures that all components $L_{<n}$ of the level L_n will increase their life expectancy significantly.

As noted previously, the natural selection of an even-leveled individual L_{n-2} slows down when it is within a higher level L_{n-1} and practically stops within a species 2 levels higher L_n . This slowdown is also true for the death expectancy, an individual within a species 2 levels higher will practically become amortal and live hundreds of times longer than the same individual in the wild. For instance, RNA barely survives in water, yet inside a virus, it can survive hours or days and even longer inside a prokaryote. Again, a non-dormant prokaryote cannot survive the 0.1-100 years that some eukaryotes survive in animals.

The same reasoning further applies to humans. Apes in the wild do not have the same life expectancy of 60-80 years that humans have. However, as civilization transitions to L_6 , individual human life expectancy will increase drastically to thousands of years. Already, vaccines allow to prevent viral infections, and antibiotics allow to defeat bacterial infections. Recent advances in immunotherapies slowly bring us to a cure for different cancers, and artificial intelligence applied to health care will allow faster drug development, diagnosis, and personalized treatments.

Key ideas

Eusocial animals such as ants and bees have an advanced social structure, but without a PMD, they could not develop a greater civilization, impose their rule, and dominate other species as humans do.

Australian Firehawk

The Australian black kite, known as *Firehawk*, is the only animal known to use fire for hunting. It takes burning branches from forest fires or camping sites and propagates them to start wildfires and force its prey to escape. Although it does not truly control fire (cannot start or maintain it), it is the closest contender to reach L_5 if humans did not exist.

Key ideas

With each new level L_n , the species $L_{<n}$ composing it will significantly increase their lifespan. We should expect humans to be amortal soon since we are transitioning to level L_6 , meaning that humans will be more likely to die from civilization collapse than aging.

Amortality

Defined in the *Sapiens* book [20], an amortal human cannot die from disease or old age, although it can still die from non-natural causes such as a car explosion.

Soon, as human civilizations will practically cure aging as it evolves to reach L_6 ; it will be more likely that a human dies from its civilization collapsing than from aging. Of course, amortality does not mean that a human cannot die from an accident/assassination or a disposal mechanism, but death from age will be very unlikely. Further, accidents and assassinations will also be unlikely since the L_6 species will have deep control over its individuals, and that individuals will require little movement thanks to the automation of resources and information transport.

4.6 Fast transition to L_6 ?

When looking at the timeline of the apparition of levels of life, one can observe gaps of hundreds of millions of years between levels. The earliest prokaryotic life is thought to have appeared $\sim 4G$ (billions) years ago, $500M$ (millions) years after the Earth formed, followed by the eukaryotes $\sim 2G$ years ago, the animals with digestive tract $\sim 541M$ years ago, and the earliest Homo Sapiens $\sim 0.2M$ years ago.

So how is the Planeta Hominis L_6 appearing so quickly after L_5 ? All other levels required hundreds of millions of years to transition.

We do not have a definite answer for this question but believe the main reason is the size of the planet compared to the size L_5 life forms: the Earth is too small for homo sapiens societies. Over the last thousands of years, they found themselves repeatedly lacking territory to expand and lacking resources. A few empires, considered here as L_5 life, controlled most of the Earth. For example, the British Empire controlled 26% of the total land, while the Mongols controlled 18% [75].

With such a small land to occupy, empires were constantly competing, at war, and finding new ways to destroy each other. This rapid increase in destructive capabilities eventually led to a fast improvement of language/communication (writing, printing, radio) and more powerful weapons. Wars between empires would only stop with the discovery of the nuclear bomb [20], [67].

In the future, the transition to L_7 is expected to be slow if interstellar travel is simple to accomplish. However, if interstellar travel is too complex, or terraformable planets are too sparse, it will eventually lead to massive planetary competition and wars for resources, and the emergence of a dominant L_7 species should happen quickly.

Further, the timeline of the RNA world L_1 to prokaryotes L_2 transition is unknown. Using the same reasoning, we can assume that if the origin of the RNA-world was confined to small and isolated hydrothermal vents, then the origin of prokaryotes should have happened shortly after the origin of the RNA-world ($\sim 1M$ years) due to strong competitive pressure. However, if the RNA-world was a giant chemical soup that covered the oceans, then L_2 would have appeared long after L_1 and the RNA-world would have been dominant for hundreds of millions of years.

Key ideas

Although each level is typically separated by hundreds of millions of years, the L_6 transition happened shortly after L_5 was completed. This is believed to be due to the small size of the planet and the limited number of accessible resources. This led to continuous wars between empires, and the quick development of nuclear weapons to finally end war.

4.7 The perception of time

An interesting point with the presented theory of life is that time is experienced differently at different levels of life. Levels $L_{0,1,2}$ experience time in a probabilistic way based on quantum mechanics. Levels $L_{3,4,5}$ experience time linearly according to the classical mechanics, while levels $L_{6,7,8}$ experience space-time according to the theory of relativity.

4.7.1 Quantum probabilistic time

For the lowest level of life that exists at the quantum scale, it is no surprise that they experience time in a probabilistic manner due to the uncertain nature of quantum mechanics. Hence, they cannot make decisions and start processes in a deterministic manner. Any action from viruses and prokaryotes is based on molecules' random fluctuations and interactions.

For example, with viruses L_1 , they do not choose to attack cells; rather they simply exist and are transported by fluids until activated by a random interaction between their protein and cellular walls. Again, for prokaryotes L_2 , decisions are not linear; they are triggered by random fluctuations and reactions within and around the cell wall.

4.7.2 Linear time

For eukaryotes L_3 , the perception of time starts to change since random fluctuations have less impact on the cell's behavior.

First, the nucleus membrane around the DNA shields it from random fluctuations and allows more stability. Further, epigenetics allows tuning genetic expression depending on environmental changes, allowing a strong control of the cell's behavior.

Further, in L_3 colonies, greater population sizes and cellular synchronicity allow redundancy of the information, reducing the randomness of decisions and resource gathering. The reduced stochasticity experimented by each cell means that the colony's behavior becomes deterministic and that it experiences time linearly.

The same linear perception of time still applies to animals, with nervous systems and brains behaving predictably. Again, with human tribes L_5 , decisions are taken assuming linear progress of time.

Note that individual cells still experiment time in a random fashion dictated by quantum fluctuations. However, the more complex cell structure and the macro-decision made by the colonies are no longer random. For instance, each part of the neural cell behaves stochastically, but with a large number of synapses and with a large number of neural cells composing the nervous system, the whole brain behaves deterministically in response to certain stimuli.

4.7.3 Space-time and a-temporal

For larger levels $L_{6,7,8}$ where species are at least the size of planets, the laws of classical physics no longer apply. Decisions made by Planeta Hominis L_6 are no longer linear in

Key ideas

The perception of time changes for each group of 3 levels. Levels $L_{0,1,2}$ experience a probabilistic time that is dictated by the randomness of quantum mechanics. Levels $L_{3,4,5}$ experience a linear and deterministic time similar to humans. Levels $L_{6,7,8}$ experience space-time as dictated by the theory of relativity.

time but must consider the space-time continuum described by the theory of relativity. This space-time usage is already observed in governmental programs such as satellites, rockets, and GPS, which use travel speed and the gravitational field to evaluate time propagation.

As life expands to even higher levels $L_{7,8}$, these living will be relying even more on the theory of relativity for their decision making and will even be able to bend space-time and navigate through the continuum. L_8 will become an a-temporal being, meaning that it will live both in the past and present. It will experience completely different laws of physics.

4.8 Ecosystem energy

An important aspect of the theory is that a life that starts to transition to a higher level will expand rapidly, destroy other species, and use them as resources. Further, odd levels start farming other livings of the same level to maximize their resources.

For the transitioning species to avoid starvation, other species must be plentiful and efficient at producing energy and growing quickly. Hence, millions of years before the transition happens, massive populations of energy-efficient species must have existed to fuel a rich ecosystem.

Thermal energy. Before the RNA-world first appeared, there must have been some efficient mechanism L_0 that could use the energy from hydrothermal vents (or other heat sources) to produce organic compounds. Similarly, for prokaryotes L_2 to appear, some RNA species at L_1 must have been very efficient at reproducing, creating amino acids, and assembling proteins. There are still bacteria living in isolated places next to heat sources.

Solar energy. For the rise of L_2 , eukaryotes required a tremendous number of resources compared to previous levels. Cyanobacteria provided this energy thanks to photosynthesis. Using the same solar energy, complex animals L_4 appeared thanks to the presence of algae and humans L_5 appeared thanks to the dominance of plants.

Nuclear energy. For the next levels $L_{6,7,8}$, nuclear energy will be the major source of power, with L_6 controlling nuclear fusion and fission and L_7 controlling the life and death of stars.

Note that there is a correlation between the type of energy used and the perception of time. Species on the quantum timescale rely on thermal energy, those on the linear time rely on solar energy, and those on the space-time scale rely on nuclear energy.

Key ideas

An energy-rich ecosystem must exist before a transition to a new level is possible, with the energy source changing every 3 levels. $L_{0,1,2}$ rely on thermal energy, $L_{3,4,5}$ on solar energy and $L_{6,7,8}$ on nuclear energy.

4.9 Validating the theory

The presented theory encompasses many elements, including the origin of life and human civilization, the classification of life into levels, and the generalization of consciousness. However, for the theory to be useful, one must be able to make accurate predictions, which is challenging since the work addresses extremely rare events that span millions of years. Instead, this section discusses some of the implications of the theory that are still open for debate. It will further provide an intuition of how to simulate the origin of life on a computer.

4.9.1 Origin of life and complex life

As mentioned in previous sections, the origin of viruses and prokaryotes is still an open question in biology [2]–[4], [18], [63], [76]. This work claims that the RNA world must have pre-dated the prokaryotes [3], [31]. It also claims that targeted catalysis is the fundamental property of RNA that allowed their emergence and eventually led to self-reproduction [18]. Again, it claims that targeted editing allowed DNA to overtake the RNA world and led to the first prokaryotes. Another claim is that if the L_1 were limited to small-scale hydro-thermal vents, high selective pressure would have forced the transition to L_2 to happen quickly on an evolutionary scale (less than a million years), as long as enough resources and diversity were present.

Unfortunately, all the above claims are difficult to verify in a laboratory setting. Indeed, the events span thousands or millions of years and require complex ecosystems for the transitioning species to thrive. We hope that the predicted pathways for the origin of life will help guide researchers towards the most likely solutions.

4.9.2 Computational simulations of life on Earth

Another approach is to use computers to simulate an artificial life form that is not necessarily organic. The simulation would consist of a few sets of rules defining level L_0 . An example is Conway's *game of life* that uses a simple set of rules to define the evolution of white pixels on a black background [77] or the Primordial Particle System (PPS) that uses basic laws of motion [78]. The simulation would require a **very, very large** and diverse environment that changes depending on the location to increase diversity.

Key ideas

It is very difficult to confirm the proposed theory by validating its predictions in labs or simulations. Indeed, predictions are made for rare events that span millions of years.

This section highlights some key predictions of the origin of life, and how to simulate it on a computer.

Conway's *Game of Life*

Conway's game of life is a cellular automata with simple rules. It is a simulation consisting of a grid with dead or alive pixels. At each simulation step, the pixels that are dead or alive depend on the neighbours at the previous step. With these rules, one can build highly complex systems.

Since life is about destruction and consumption, we believe that the conservation of mass is one of the most important rules for the simulation. Indeed, this will give an advantage to the simulated structures that can consume other structures, not just destroying them. With enough resources and time, this could lead to the rise of a structure that controls a PMD over others, meaning that it found a mechanism to consume any other structures for its growth.

Leaving the simulation to pure randomness would take too much time, but it is an important first step to reach diversity. Once diversity is large enough, the simulation could give *bonuses* to more aggressive structures. These bonuses will put strong pressure on an arms race and hopefully accelerate the development of a PMD. Once a species develops a powerful weapon that allows it to dominate the entire simulation, it will increase in size and develop minor structures for information storage and protection similar to a virus. It will also start farming some other species within the simulation, eventually leading to an L_1 species.

Simulating an L_2 species could be done via similar steps, although it would be exponentially more expensive due to the exponential increase in size. If such simulation is successful, one would observe that the L_2 species become so large as to take a significant percentage of the simulation space. It will also develop much more complex structures, highways to transfer information and resources, and automated machines that accomplish specific tasks.

Although the simulation path is more realistic than the lab-testing, it would still require tremendous work, effort, and computation to achieve. We propose the following rules for the simulation.

- **A 3D simulation on a grid.** The grid must be extremely large to ensure diversity but also to ensure that large structures, L_1 and L_2 species have enough space and resources to thrive. We believe a grid of size **at least $10^5 \times 10^5 \times 10^5$** is necessary, totaling 10^{15} pixels. This number is intractable with current computers as it requires 1PB of space just for the environment and millions of simulation steps.
- **Each pixel receives an amount of energy** that depends on its position. The energy per position varies slowly in time, with some rare abrupt changes to trigger diversity.
- **Each pixel is a different color**, representing an atom type, with unique properties and rules. The rules should include interaction with other colors, the amount of captured energy, etc. One can base the rules on the atomic properties of the most common atoms to create similar structures.
- **Energy is used to move or create bonds**, similar to quantum mechanics.
- **Interactions must have randomness.** Otherwise, the simulation will favor stable crystal structures.
- **Law of the conservation of mass:** Atoms are never destroyed, only moved.
- **Atoms sinks and faucets:** The above rule has some exceptions. There are sinks/faucets located at sparse locations that eliminate/produce specific atom types or structures. The sinks/faucets will simulate volcanoes and hydrothermal vents and increase diversity.
- **A canonical way of describing structures** similar to the notion of molecules. These structures will be studied to detect life during the simulation.

Primordial Particle System

PPS is a particle simulation with simple rules: the motion of each particle depends on its previous motion and the other particles near it, with a very simple equation. It was shown to produce self-reproducing structures with life-like properties under different configurations. They are not considered alive by the proposed theory since they lack a PMD to destroy nearby structures.

- **Engineer structures that can catalyze** a variety of reactions depending on their structure. These will mimic the function of RNA and accelerate the simulations' convergence.

The above rules are not original. They try to mimic how the origin of life happened on Earth by reproducing atoms, quantum mechanics, and energy vents. However, the rules were carefully selected to increase the diversity of structures while enabling an evolutionary advantage to destroy other structures and gather their resources. Hopefully, these rules will yield analogs to RNA and DNA.

Even with enough computational resources, the above rules face major uncertainty. Can a PMD exist in a grid structure? How many hyper-parameters should be tried until we find life? Is it feasible to simulate such a system on a classical computer? How much time does the simulation need to yield life? What is the probability of life emerging under the right parameters?

4.9.3 Non-3D life?

Why not simplify the simulation to a 2D grid to exponentially reduce the computation time? In a 2D world, there are only 3 degrees of freedom (horizontal, vertical, and rotation) compared to the 6 degrees of freedom of a 3D world. This limited degree of freedom could prevent a PMD from existing since defensive structures would be very difficult to destroy. For example, kingdoms protected themselves from invasion by building walls around themselves that restrict the 2D movement of humans. The walls made it practically impossible to conquer cities unless the invader uses the third dimension to throw weapons above the wall, climb over it, or dig under it. The same argument could be made on the microscopic scale: chemical structures would be too stable, implying that PMDs could not evolve that life could not exist in a 2D world.

This point must also be considered for *in vitro* experiments. Indeed, it would be difficult to reproduce the emergence of life in very thin films. The experiment must allow enough degrees of freedom.

For 4D worlds, the interactions might be too unstable and reactive to form cohesive and stable structures. Thus, there cannot exist a PMD that destroys other structures to its advantage: all structures are constantly being destroyed, thus implying that life could not exist in 4D.

Hence, 3D seems to be the ideal Universe dimensionality for life to exist, a result identical to quantum theory [79]. In 2D, PMDs cannot evolve since structures are too stable. In 4D, complex structures cannot evolve since reactivity is too high. However, this point remains a speculation to be tested via simulations.

Key ideas

Can life exist in a non-3D space? It is difficult to answer as life could take forms that we can't imagine. However, it seems unlikely that a PMD could evolve in 2D since structures would be too stable and difficult to attack. In 4D, reactivity would be too high for complex structures to evolve. Perhaps 3D is the ideal Universe dimensionality for life to exist?

4.10 Destroying the Universe

From the perspective of the current theory, not only does life arise from the acquisition of a PMD, but this given power of mass destruction increases exponentially at each level. Likewise, life's ability to find and extract resources increases exponentially.

From this theory, multiple philosophical questions arise naturally. Is the purpose of life to destroy the Universe? Is it the inevitable legacy of humanity to destroy the Earth and its ecosystems? Will our descendants consume the whole universe?

This section tries to answer these questions, although they are left open to debate since they are philosophical questions, and we prefer to focus on scientific questions.

4.10.1 The purpose of life?

First, we would like to mention that there does not need to be a purpose to life. The notion of *purpose* is a human concept; life can exist without meaning. Still, we present a short answer to satisfy our philosophical curiosity.

From the perspective of the proposed theory, if life has a purpose, its purpose is to destroy the Universe by accelerating its entropic decay. From the very first species L_1 that learned to destroy and assemble simple chemical compounds, to the more advanced L_7 species that will destroy stars, it seems that life never stops consuming resources and destroying matter at an exponentially growing scale.

Most importantly, life always finds a way to survive, reproduce and expand beyond expected limits. Eukaryotes can survive in places inhospitable for prokaryotes, and Humans can travel between planets. Given enough time, there is no resource out of reach from life. Hence, life is completely different from standard physical processes that mostly interact with nearby objects; life tries to interact with everything everywhere.

4.10.2 Saving the ecosystem

With the purpose of life being to destroy the Universe, what does it say about planet Earth? Are humans doomed to destroying the ecosystem? Is it inevitable? Here, we argue that saving the ecosystem is part of humans' purpose.

If humans are to maximize the entropic demise of the Universe and to terraform planets with little effort, then a large biodiversity is needed. Spreading complex ecosystems to various planets will make it easier and faster to colonize planets and increase the amount of useful resources.

4.10.3 A human-centric universe

With humans being the only species to travel willingly between planets and the solar system, it is no surprise that all life in the Universe will depend on humans for expansion. Most species will either evolve as symbionts or as parasites to *Planeta Hominis*.

Key ideas

The purpose of life seems to be the destruction of the Universe and the consumption of all its resources.

Humans will become central to all other life-forms in spreading them across planets. Most life forms will become either symbionts or parasites to humans.

A similar process is also observed for lower levels. For example, simple organic compounds L_0 deteriorate quickly in the wild but get to live and spread in different environments inside viruses and prokaryotes. Again, viruses and prokaryotes could not survive and spread across desertic lands (across oceans, mountains, continents), but thanks to the ecosystem built by plants and animals, they can easily survive and spread in otherwise desertic areas. Bacteria living in fish or whales can travel across oceans instead of being confined to local environments, while bacteria living in elephants can travel across the African continent.

4.11 A new definition of life

The natural way to conclude this work is to provide a new and simpler definition of life that does not rely on observed characteristics but rather on the organism itself. Thus, it does not exclude life forms different than anything observed and stops the debate about whether viruses and bacterial spores are alive.

4.11.1 Definition

Life is an n-leveled fractal of equilibrium collaborative ecosystems that controls a targeted power of mass destruction (PMD) at each level. It uses the PMDs to consume and process resources at different scales.

Collaborative ecosystem is a composition of interacting individuals that share resources and information.

Equilibrium ecosystem means that the interaction between individuals in an ecosystem is stable and changes very little over time.

Fractal ecosystem means that within each individual of an ecosystem, recursively, there exists a smaller ecosystem with the same goal, with the lowest level being the building blocks.

Hence, this work provides a definition of life based on its function as an organism. This definition differs from standard biology that defines life by its observed characteristics, such as its ability to reproduce, its composition of organic matter, its death, and its evolution via natural selection. Using the provided definition, one can retrieve the standard definition of life without being limited to these characteristics. Depending on the environment, life can change its behavior and defy some of the common characteristics.

4.11.2 Retrieving the standard definition of life

The standard definition of life includes reproduction, organic matter, death, and experiencing natural selection. Below, we explain how all these elements are a simple case of our broader definition.

Reproduction: Reproduction is an optimal strategy to increase the consumption of resources and maintain an ecosystem equilibrium since it allows a species to cover

Life (standard definition)

A characteristic of physical entities that have biological processes, determined functions, can reproduce, experience natural selection, are made of organic matter, and experience death.

Note: This definition is a simple enumeration of characteristics that were found with life on Earth, and doesn't take into account the different levels of complexity.

Life (our definition)

Life is an n-leveled fractal of equilibrium collaborative ecosystems that controls a targeted power of mass destruction (PMD) at each level. It uses the PMDs to consume and process resources at different scales.

Note: This definition is broader and not limited to what is observed on Earth. Yet it is more precise, making it easier to answer if any particular structure is alive, and at what level.

more territory and create redundancy to prevent collapse. However, reproduction is only a good strategy when resources are plentiful and the environment is not hostile. In a hostile environment, life can stop reproducing, as is evident in bacterial spores or animals' hibernation, but it does not stop being alive. In our definition, this behavior is consistent with preserving the ecosystem and shows that reproduction is only an ideal strategy under certain circumstances. Again, viruses cannot reproduce by themselves, and with eusocial animals, only the queen can. Under the standard definition, they should not be considered alive; yet our definition considers them alive since self-reproduction is not mandatory.

Made of organic matter: The lowest fractal level is the organic matter for commonly observed life. However, this is a very limiting definition. Life could exist in forms and shapes that we cannot imagine, or life could exist as inorganic matter such as robots or software, and this theory does not exclude them.

Death: As the ecosystems of life are at equilibrium, death is simply the collapse of the equilibrium. Again, death is not necessary to satisfy the criteria for being alive.

Natural selection: Since life consumes resources to expand, there will naturally be a clash when territories overlap. However, life must preserve its fractal ecosystem nature. Thus, the interaction cannot be mutually destructive, meaning that clashes are competitive rather than destructive. This competitive behavior yields to the theory of natural selection.

4.11.3 Auto-catalytic systems

Some physical processes, such as black holes or hurricanes, also consume resources and expand. However, they do not need to preserve the underlying ecosystem. Thus, mutually destructive interactions are possible (and the norm) for physical processes, meaning they do not follow natural selection.

Crystals are also structures known to consume surrounding atoms or molecules to grow in size. However, they do not control a PMD, meaning they cannot process any atom or molecule and add it to the crystal. The crystal will only grow and consume under the appropriate conditions.

Many researchers propose that auto-catalytic systems or networks are responsible for the origin of nucleic acids (RNA and DNA), which eventually led to the emergence of life [4], [5]. This point of view aligns with the presented hypothesis that targeted catalysis is responsible for the origin of life by allowing RNA to transform surrounding molecules into useful compounds. However, the auto-catalysis network is not the first step. The first step that started the transition $L_{0 \rightarrow 1}$ is the catalysis of many different organic reactions. It could lead to the growth of the RNA, the creation of complementary structures, the production of other RNA to catalyze different reactions, or the increase in the complexity of surrounding organic molecules. Self-reproduction by auto-catalysis represents the full control of the PMD at the end of the transition.

5 Conclusion

In summary, our work proposes a major shift in how we view and study life on Earth and allows us to deepen our general understanding of life, how it appeared, and how it can exist in non-organic forms. With the simple premise that **levels of life originate from controlled mass destruction**, our theory generalizes the origin of life, complex life, Cambrian explosion, and human civilization with a single explanation. It further generalizes information processing, domestication, automation, and consciousness to all life forms.

One of the major advantages of the proposed theory is that comparing the different levels of life allows us to fill up gaps in our understanding of the past and the future of life. For example, knowing that odd levels are similar, we can better understand RNA-life's origin by looking at the origin of eukaryotes and Homo Sapiens. With the same idea, we can better predict the future of Planeta Hominis by looking at how Eukaryotic colonies became complex animals.

A less fortunate conclusion is that human's superior intelligence was not the main factor in building civilization. Rather, it was human's superior ability to destroy everything. Intelligence and social skills were simply ways of increasing the efficiency of our destructive abilities while avoiding self-annihilation. As we currently transition to the next level L_6 , we must be aware that our destructive power is immense and must be extremely careful in using it, especially knowing that all life on Earth is doomed to become symbionts or parasites of humanity to spread in the Universe.

Humans are destroyers of worlds. But so were the first prokaryote and the first animal with a full digestive tract.

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Appendix

A. Artificial intelligence

A popular subject of science fiction and scientific debate is whether artificial intelligence (AI) will surpass humans and take over the world one day. This section answers whether the proposed theory allows it to happen and under what conditions.

First, remember the definition of life as a fractal of collaborative ecosystems at different levels, possessing a PMD over each lower level. In a world with advanced AI, the level L_0 species are all the robots and algorithms with specific purposes. The advanced AI would be a species that wants to transition $L_{0 \rightarrow 1}$. To achieve the transition, it must control a power that allows it to mass-destroy them and consume their resources for its growth. One can imagine the PMD as an unstoppable computer virus that permanently enslaves other machines to use their computational and hardware resources to improve itself.

However, to become fully alive, the AI needs also to control a PMD over humans due to the *first-in, last-in* problem. This scary conclusion means that the AI only becomes alive if it exterminates humanity. Otherwise, it is simply an automated machine for use by Planeta Hominis. To stop this from happening, AI developers must ensure that the machine will never desire to be alive since life arises from destruction. Once humans fully reach L_6 , their destructive power will be too strong, and their spread too large, that we are guaranteed not to be overtaken by AI. Nevertheless, during the transition period, things are uncertain.

One must remember that humans will also become smarter via organic and inorganic augmentations. Their brains will be connected to the internet and enhanced with computational chips. Thus, the AI will not succeed by being smarter than a single human; it will compete with the hive-mind of Planeta Hominis and must be able to destroy the hive mind to become alive. Hence, both the brain-implemented chips and their network must be un-hackable and impossible to shut down; otherwise, it opens the door to AI overtaking humanity by destroying the hive mind.

Looking back at history, levels L_2 and L_4 also developed life-like automated machines, yet they never overtook the host; they became an integrated part. From this perspective, we can also imagine that the AI will become an integrated part of Planeta Hominis, not its enemy, but nothing is certain.